

Blood Culture Positive Infections in Maintenance Hemodialysis -Clinical Profile in a South Indian Tertiary Care Hospital

Running title: Blood Infections in Maintenance Hemodialysis

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Authorship Contribution:

Author name	Conceived and designed the analysis	Collected the data	Contributed data or analysis tools	Performed the analysis	Wrote the paper	Others
Arun S	✓	✓			✓	
Disha A		✓	✓	✓	✓	
Mayoor Prabhu	✓	✓			✓	
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Ethical considerations:

Study was conducted after obtaining Institutional Ethical Committee Clearance (**IEC KMC MLR 04-17/69**). Anonymity of participants was safeguarded by not linking any patient identifying details to the study data. Written consent of participants was taken after explaining the participants the study and clarifying their doubts if any. Project was performed in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

ABSTRACT:

Background - Infections in individuals with Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) undergoing hemodialysis are more prone to other diseases as well as fatalities. Predisposing causes for infections in such cases are unclear. Identification of at-risk patients could help at mitigating these risk factors and help in more targeted interventions, for better prognosis. This will help in achieving the third goal of “Good Health and Well-Being” of the 17 **Sustainable Developmental Goals as described by United Nations.**

Methods- Institute’s Ethics Committee clearance was attained. In this cross sectional study, 100 patients on maintenance hemodialysis (MHD) for >1 month were randomly selected. Retrospective data for blood culture positive bacterial infections in past 6 months was collected through hospital records. Patients were followed up for the next 3 months. Demographic data, and data on associated comorbidities, type of vascular access Central Venous Catheters (CVC) or Arteriovenous Fistula/Graft (AVF/AVG) was collected. Blood culture reports of all these patients were analyzed. Correlations between infections and access-point, culture positivity, causative organisms, comorbidities, and predisposition for future infection at other sites were analyzed.

Results – 15% patients had AVF, 85% CVC. Diabetes Mellitus (DM) was main etiology of CKD (70%). 49% had blood culture positive infections in the past 6 months with Staphylococcus (n=11) being most common isolate followed by Escherichia coli (n=77), Klebsiella (n=7), Enterobacter etc. Statistically significant positive correlation between AVF and culture positive infections was noted. Patients also demonstrated tendency for infections at other sites within 3 month period.

Conclusion – Patients on MHD demonstrated predisposition to access site infection. They were susceptible to infection at other sites like respiratory tract infections, urinary tract infections etc. Thus, patients developing access site related infections need monitoring and thorough investigation to prevent future complications.

Keywords: Arterio-venous fistula, bacteremia, central venous access, chronic kidney disease

INTRODUCTION

Globally Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) is evolving as one of the prevalent chronic diseases that needs more consideration ^(1, 2). It may be due to rapid upsurge in overall incidence of Diabetes Mellitus (DM) and hypertension (HTN) ⁽³⁾. With rise in CKD cases and the large number of inhabitants within India, both national healthcare and economic facilities are under challenge. A study quoted that in India, End Stage Renal Disease (ESRD) has an age-adjusted incidence rate of 229 per million population (pmp), and more than lakh fresh cases require kidney related treatments every year ⁽⁴⁾. With limited resources, hardly 10% of Indian ESRD cases are provided with Renal Replacement Therapy (RRT) ⁽⁵⁾. Nearly 85% of centers in India having dialysis facilities are private organizations and conduct transplant-related dialysis in addition to maintenance hemodialysis (MHD) ⁽⁶⁾.

Majority MHD patients succumb majorly to bacterial infections. Incidence of bacterial infections is almost one episode/100 patient-months ^(7, 8, 9). Causes as noted for the same are nasal presence of Staphylococcus Aureus and/ or previous episodes of bacterial infection. Other risk factors include iron overload, hypoalbuminemia, dialysis through central venous catheters rather than an AVF, usage of bio incompatible membranes and elevated serum ferritin (>500 pg/L) ^(10, 11, 12, 13). Notably, infections are associated with significant healthcare expenditure ⁽¹⁴⁾. This will help in achieving the third goal of “Good Health and Well-Being” of the 17 Sustainable Developmental Goals as described by United Nations.

OBJECTIVES:

Aim of our work was to study the clinical profile of CKD cases on MHD, evaluate them for episodes of infections, determine causative agent by studying patient’s microbiological profile and identify risk/ predisposing factors for access site infections in CKD patients on MHD.

METHODOLOGY

Study population

We conducted a cross sectional study during April 2017 to July 2017, in Tertiary Care hospitals affiliated to Medical College in a city of coastal South India. Being a time bound study, our study included randomly selected 100 patients, who had been on MHD for more than one month.

Data collection

Retrospective data for bacterial infections among patients on maintenance hemodialysis in the past 6 months was collected through hospital records and these patients were followed up for the next 3 months. New cases admitted or detected during the study period were as well considered in our study, their laboratory investigations done and followed up for 3 months. Patients complaining of fever with other constitutional symptoms like malaise, chills, rigors etc. were considered to have an infectious episode and their blood culture was done. Demographic data -age, gender, along with associated comorbidities -DM, Hypertension (HTN), malignancy, etc. were collected through self- structured questionnaire. Predisposing factors like cannula /catheter usage, type of vascular access (AVF/AVG), catheter –site (internal jugular vein, femoral vein), past infection reported due to catheter usage were also recorded.

Microbiological methods for culture and isolation

Under complete aseptic precaution blood was withdrawn for blood culture analysis of all study patients. Blood samples collected from patients were sent to microbiology laboratory. Identification of organisms was done after a series of processes. Automated blood culture system (BacT/ ALERT; bioMeriux, Inc. Durham, North California, USA) was used to obtain blood culture of samples. Gram staining was done of the smear prepared from the specimens obtained from positive blood culture bottles. Blood agar, Chocolate agar, and MacConkey agar were utilized for further subculture assessment of the positive blood culture samples. After an overnight aerobic incubation at 37⁰C on completing 24 hours, these cultured plates were

inspected. Organisms were recognized based on their colonial morphology, Gram staining and appropriate conventional biochemical tests and Vitek 2 Compact system (bioMeriux, Inc.Durham, USA). The interpretation of results was based on the recommendations of Clinical Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI). Each culture positive sample was recorded with following details – patient details, date and causative organism.

Data analysis

Data entry and analysis was done using IBM SPSS for Windows version 16.0, Armonk, New York. The descriptive statistics for categorical variables were presented as percentages and frequencies. p value <0.05 was used as criterion for significance. Since the study was qualitative with categorical variables Chi – square test was performed.

RESULTS

100 patients initiated on MHD in the past 6 months were included. Age of participants ranged from 20-90 years with mean age being 59.2 ± 13.5 years. **Table 1** illustrates the demographic details.

Table no. 1: General Demographic findings among participants (n=100)

Sl. No.	Demographic characteristics	Frequency
1.	Patients suffering from CKD undergoing dialysis	100
2.	Gender a. Male b. Female	69 31
3.	Age in years • Min • Maximum (Mean - 59.20 ± 13.494)	20 90
4.	Blood report a. Bacteremia present b. Bacteremia absent	49 51

Out of 10 participants in study, 69 were males, 21 were females. DM was main etiology of CKD (70%). Among other comorbidities 9% of patients had coronary artery disease (CAD), 9% pneumonia, 3 patients had malignancy and 3 patients had chronic liver disease (CLD). Of

70 diabetic patients, 68% had a blood culture positive infection. For majority (85%) of patients, dialysis access was through central venous catheter pending AVF/AVG creation. 15% had a functioning AVF. **Figure 1** shows distribution of patients based upon culture report and comorbidities.

Figure 1: Classification of Hemodialysis Patients Based on Access Pattern:

Under complete aseptic precaution blood was withdrawn for blood culture analysis of all study patients, of these 49 were found to have bacteremia. Most common organism was *Staphylococcus* (n=16). Different species of *Staphylococci* were isolated, majority being *Staphylococcus aureus* (n=8), Coagulase Negative *Staphylococcus* CoNS (n=4), *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (n=3), *Staphylococcus hominis* (n=1). *E. coli* was next most common organism, found in 11 cultures, followed by *Klebsiella* and *Enterobacter* (n=7 each). We also obtained 4 blood cultures with *Candida*, 3 blood cultures of *Streptococcus* and 1 blood culture which had *Citrobacter*.

Figure 2: Culture growth of micro-organisms in different patients

11 patients (73.3%) with AV fistula and 38 patients out of 85 patients with central venous catheter (44.6%) had positive blood culture reports, as seen in **Table – 2**. When an association was sought between a bacteria positive culture and type of access, Chi square value was 4.181 which is statistically significant for AVF.

Table 2: Access Pattern Versus Culture Positive Sample

Access pattern	Culture positive	Culture negative	Total
Central venous line	38	47	85
Arterio – venous fistula	11	4	15
Total	49	51	100

*p - 0.041

Also one of significant findings in our study was that out of 49 CKD patients with blood culture positive infections 24 patients had developed infections at other body sites apart from the vascular access, (**Table -3**) noted within 3 months of our study. 9 patients developed pneumonia, urinary tract infection (n=6), sacroiliac abscess (n=2), lung abscess(n=2), and acute suppurative otitis media (n=1).

Table 3: Associated comorbidities in culture positive patients

Comorbid conditions	Bacterial culture positive
Diabetes mellitus	48
Hypertension	32
Pneumonia,	9
Urinary Tract Infection	6
Sacroiliac Abscess	2
Lung Abscess	2
Acute Suppurative Otitis Media	1
Sepsis	4

Figure 3: Culture Positivity Based on Associated Comorbidities.

Further, patients with culture positive reports were statistically correlated with their medical history of presence or absence of DM and HTN. There was positive correlation between presence of these diseases and culture positive reports, however it was not statistically significant.

DISCUSSION

In this observational study, we analyzed a cohort of randomly selected 100 patients on MHD. We found patients with vascular access had secondary infections, and these were more common among those with associated comorbidities. In our study, diabetic patients with CKD

having infections was more (n=49).

Studies have shown infection as a recurrent reason for both morbidity and mortality in CKD patients on MHD. Studies propose that infection is next major cause of fatality in cases with CKD^(2, 15, 16). This raised predisposition to infections can be somewhat ascribed to malfunctioning phagocytosis of granulocytes, uremia related compromised immune status, increased age, recurrent tendency of patients getting exposed to latent/ impending communicable infective factors while undergoing routine prescribed dialysis therapy and dominance of DM in terms of prevalence^(17, 18).

Of the patients where bacteremia was found with a positive blood culture, *Staphylococcus* was most commonly identified pathogen (fig 2). This is consistent with other studies which have shown a high prevalence of *S aureus* and *E. coli* among organisms causing bacteremic episodes in CKD. In a study by Berman SJ, *S aureus*, CoNS, *P. aeruginosa*, *E. coli*, *Klebsiella*, and *Enterobacter* were the other microorganisms isolated more frequently⁽¹⁹⁾.

High prevalence of *Staphylococcus* in blood cultures in our study may perhaps have another predisposing factor; to develop such an infection, other body sites may harbor and be a source of infection, such as nasal carriage of *S. aureus*, as documented by another study⁽²⁰⁾. Patients on MHD are predisposed to bacterial infections of varied strains in terms of Gram staining. Among Gram-Positive organisms, *S. Aureus* and Coagulase-Negative *Staphylococci* (CoNS) carry the major onus of being the most frequent infective agents. Infections by facultative anaerobic enterococci, another Gram-positive bacterium, are also being increasingly noticed. One of the major pitfalls in treatment course of blood-borne infections in hemodialysis cases is inadequacy in available routes for vascular access⁽¹⁶⁾. Complementing these problems, the upsurge in resistance to vancomycin in these contagions has projected a grave implication for future management of infections⁽¹⁷⁾.

There were about 51 MHD patients in our study who presented with fever, chills and were suspected of a bacteremia episode, following which a blood culture was sent. However, no growth was detected in 2 patient samples. In another case-mix study based on the U.S. Renal Data System having a data of seven years of follow-up, authors found increasing age and

diabetes both raised chances of incurring septicemia in dialysis patients ⁽²¹⁾.

In our study of 100 patients, 70 had DM, of these 48 patients (68.5%) had a blood culture positive report (Table 3, Fig 3). Complications through vascular entry point are a major cause of prolonged sickness and even fatality among MHD patients. 11 patients (73.3%) with AV fistula had a positive blood culture and 38 of 85 patients with central line (44.6%) had positive blood culture report (Table 2). This is, however, not consistent with other studies which show that there are more risks of bacteremic episodes with central venous line than AV fistulas. This discrepancy in our time bound study could be because only a small number of patients had AV fistula in our study.

In another study, it was documented that fifty-one cases showed all together 57 incidences of infection. Of these, 44 suffered acute bacterial infections, and the most common reason was contamination through the vascular entry point, the next infective condition was septicemia (n=13) ⁽²⁰⁾.

Some other studies have shown that vascular access related infections can deteriorate patient condition through sepsis with multi organ failure, endocarditis; or metastatic infections such as vertebral osteomyelitis, epidural abscess, or endophthalmitis. Few of these complications are an absolute threat to the survival of patient. 75% deaths in hemodialysis patients can be attributed to dialysis-related bloodstream infections ⁽²¹⁾.

Among comorbidities, CAD, pneumonia, malignancy and CLD were the most common. About 65 patients had HTN, of these 32 had blood culture positive report (Table 3, Fig 3). However, there is no conclusive data about association of HTN and bacteremic episodes in CKD patients from previous studies. Perhaps more conclusive research needs to be done about whether HTN and CAD in dialysis patients increases the chance of bacteremic episodes or these are just an incidental correlation.

‘Multi-morbidity’ can be termed as suffering from two or more chronic diseases simultaneously. Patients with CKD and suffering from other comorbid conditions fall in this criteria. Comorbidities need to be considered as they play a role in altering healthcare expenditure, quality of life, and survival. Various comorbidities along with accompanying

polypharmacy affect patients' capacity to cope with treatment as described in 'burden of treatment model' ^(22, 23).

Out of 49 CKD patients with blood culture positive infections, 24 developed non access related infections when they were followed up. These infections included pneumonia, UTI, sepsis, sacroiliac abscess, lung abscess, and acute suppurative otitis media. These observations are similar to other studies which document the occurrence of high levels of respiratory tract infections, sepsis, and urinary tract infections in these group of patients, possible factors could be advanced age, high burden of coexisting illnesses, hypoalbuminemia, retention of uremic toxins that deplete already deficient immune system ⁽²⁾. In our study setting, serum ferritin levels were not routinely measured as part of investigations for patients on dialysis, though this has been proposed to be an important predisposing factor to infections ⁽¹¹⁾. The association between infections and serum ferritin needs to be further evaluated in future trials. Due to time bound study, our study falls short of this analysis, thus, this is a shortcoming of our project.

With the expanding population of patients with CKD globally and associated excess morbidity and mortality, it's imperative to identify potentially modifiable risk factors to reduce the burden to patients, families, and health care system. Based on limited data, acute infections seem to occur more frequently in CKD patients, responsible for increased mortality. Further analyses of epidemiology and the impact of infections (overall and disease specific) to overall mortality in CKD can alleviate the disease burden and help patients lead effective life; prevent further infections and improve overall clinical outcomes.

Conclusion:

Patients on MHD demonstrated predisposition to access site infection. They were more susceptible to infections at other sites in the body like respiratory tract infections, urinary tract infections etc. Thus, patients developing access site related infections need monitoring and thorough investigation to prevent future complications.

Limitations:

This was a time bound student project work, hence, the number of cases studied were 100.

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